

Advantages with a large revolving scanning angle

L Lindegren, 1981 July 22

The revolving scanning angle (ξ) is the acute angle between the nominal spin axis (z) and the satellite/sun line. According to the ITT it should remain fixed throughout the mission and be in the range $36^\circ - 45^\circ$. There are strong scientific arguments in favour of a large angle (say 45°):

1. The geometrical factor. If $\xi = 0$ the telescope would scan along meridional lines of equal ecliptical longitude (λ). Since measurements are basically taken only along the scans, this would mean that only the latitudes (β) of the stars could be obtained. The determination of their longitudes depends on the finite intersection angles between the meridional lines and the scans, amounting to at most $\pm\xi$ for stars near the ecliptic. With $\xi = 45^\circ$ both components of the positions (and proper motions) could be measured to about the same accuracy; for $\xi < 45^\circ$ there is a stronger anisotropy of precision which is rather undesirable. More importantly, it can be shown that the parallactic displacement of a star along the scan is proportional to $\sin\xi$, which means that the parallax mean errors will go as $1/\sin\xi$. These factors are considered in detail in the Appendix of Ref. 1, from which the following table is derived.

ξ	relative mean errors (sky average)		
	λ (position and p.m.)	β	π (parallax)
36°	0.309	0.237	0.453
45°	0.287	0.258	0.385
improvement (rigidity)	7% (18%)	-9% (3%)	15% (25% ?)

2. Rigidity of the spherical reconstitution. This rather ill-defined concept refers to how well the ensemble of measurements can be tied together into a global system of astrometric data. Apart from the purely geometrical aspects mentioned above it involves also the correlations between different stars due to the relativeness of measurements. Since a given star is, on the average, directly connected to a larger part of the sky when ξ is increased, one expects then improved rigidity. The only numerical indications of this effect presently available are from the small-scale simulations in Ref. 1. These show a much stronger improvement of both λ and β with increasing ξ than can be attributed to the geometrical factors alone. From a rather risky extrapolation one obtains the expected improvements given in parentheses in the table above, including both the geometrical and rigidity factors.

3. Sky uniformity. The uniformity of astrometric precision, especially when comparing different latitudes, would be markedly improved for a larger ξ . The ratio of the longitude mean errors between the ecliptic and the poles is about 2.1 for $\xi = 36^\circ$ and 1.5 for $\xi = 45^\circ$. A weaker improvement is expected for the parallaxes, while the latitudes have rather uniform precision also for small ξ .

4. Resolution of double stars. The probability to detect and successfully reduce observations of double and multiple stars would improve with larger ξ , especially for stars in the ecliptical zone (which is half the sky!). This would cause the different scans across a given star to spread over a wider range of position angles (roughly $\pm\xi$ with respect to North-South direction), making the (partial) resolution of two-dimensional objects easier.

The main disadvantage of a larger ξ (from the scientific point of view) seems to be that the frequency and length of interruptions by earth and moon occultations tend to increase. With the Phase A design it appears that this would have been more than compensated by the advantages listed above; with improved straylight suppression it may be a minor problem.

Even if the generally improved accuracy could not be realized in the tradeoff against other factors, the final results could still benefit from the other advantages (rigidity, uniformity, double star detection), making a large revolving angle highly desirable.

Ref. 1 P Høyer, K Poder, L Lindegren and E Høg:
Derivation of Positions and Parallaxes from Simulated Observations
with a Scanning Astrometry Satellite (to appear in Astronomy and
Astrophysics, 1981) = ITT Information Document No. 12.